

ALL POLYPROPYLENE NANOCOMPOSITE WITH WELL-ALIGNED AND WELL-ORIENTED ELECTROSPUN POLYPROPYLENE NANOFIBERS

Takashi Nishino¹, Yuji Asahina¹, Chizuru Hongo²

¹Graduate School of Engineering, Kobe University,
Rokko, Nada, Kobe 657-8501, Japan

Email: tnishino@kobe-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www2.kobe-u.ac.jp/~tnishino/cx4.html>

²Organization of Advanced Science and Technology Kobe University,
Rokko, Nada, Kobe 657-8501, Japan

Keywords: Electrospinning, Nanocomposites, Nanofiber, Polypropylene, Single polymer composites

ABSTRACT

Isotactic polypropylene (*it*.PP) nanofibers were electrospun from conducting solution using rotating drum collector, followed by post-drawing under heat to promote crystallization and molecular orientation. The well-aligned and well-oriented *it*.PP nanofibers showed higher Young's modulus and higher tensile strength superior to the *it*.PP film. Furthermore, compared to the film, drawn nanofibers showed higher melting temperature, which enabled to *it*.PP matrix resin into *it*.PP nanofibers through melt compression. The structure and properties of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite was investigated using electron/atomic microscopes, X-ray diffraction, thermal analyses, tensile test, spectrophotometer and so on. This recyclable nanocomposite was found to show superior optical transparency and mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

it.PP shows good cost-performance such as light weight, high processability, mechanical properties and thermostability. So *it*.PP has been used in wide range of applications such as composite matrix, packaging material, textiles (e.g., ropes, thermal underwear, carpets and so on), automotive components and electrical appliances [1].

Recently, polymer composites have excellent properties so that they are used in wide range of applications such as automobiles, ICT and electronic devices, and medicals [2]. As the reinforcing elements, glass fibers or carbon fibers are often used. In general, these composites have interface between the matrix and the reinforcements. This interface often causes problems such as poor adhesion, imperfect stress transfer and high water uptake. These problems may reduce the properties of the whole composites. From this point of view, the concept of single polymer composites has proposed. The composites are made by similar or identical materials for both matrix and reinforcement, so they have advantage in terms of recyclability and interfacial compatibility. Following this pioneering works on all-polyethylene composites [3,4], all-polypropylene composite [5-7], a number of studies have been carried out on the preparation and characterization of single polymer composite. Our laboratory has also engaged in these works, e.g. *all*-cellulose composite [8,9], *all*-Aramid composite [10] and so on.

In past few decades, polymer nanoscale materials are the subject of extensive worldwide researches in both industry and academia because of their novel functionality and high performance. Especially, nanofibers can be expected to possess high mechanical properties with the significant increase of specific surface area and with the decrease of structure defects, when a fiber diameter approaches to nanometer order. Electrospinning is known as a low cost but effective method to produce polymer nanofibers [11, 12]. It is a unique approach using electrostatic forces to produce fine fibers from polymer solutions or molten polymers, and they have a smaller diameter and larger surface area than those obtained from conventional spinning process. Thus, electrospinning became well-recognized method and has already created interesting applications in drug delivery system, wound dressing,

scaffolds in tissue engineering, and sensors in electronics [13-15]. However, getting nanofiber by electrospinning of poly- α -olefines, such as *it*.PP and polyethylene, has been said to be difficult, because of high viscosity and low electron conductivity of the solution or melt [16].

In this study, *it*.PP nanofibers were prepared using electrospinning from 1,2-dichlorobenzene solution, by adding ionic substance for giving electrical conductivity to the solution, and by introducing a high-frequency heating unit into a syringe part for reducing the viscosity of solution.

In general, electrospinning is used to make nonwoven fabric. However, in this study, we basically used this electrospinning technique but there is one distinguished different point. Instead of using flat plate collector, we here used a rotating drum collector (30mm width drum), which make fibers well-aligned. Then, this well-aligned *it*.PP nanofibers could be uniaxially drawn under heating to promote crystallization and uniaxial molecular orientation, which is expected to result in higher mechanical properties. Furthermore, compared to the bulk material, these drawn nanofibers are expected to show higher melting temperature. This makes it possible to prepare *all-it*.PP nanocomposites, by using these nanofibers as reinforcement.

In this study, using *it*.PP as both matrix and reinforcement, *all-it*.PP nanocomposite were prepared. Well-aligned and well-oriented *it*.PP nanofibers, by electrospinning and post-drawing, were impregnated between *it*.PP through melt compression into *all-it*.PP nanocomposite. As the result, *it*.PP matrix were oriented parallel to the fiber axial direction of filled nanofibers. This recyclable composite showed high optical transparency, high mechanical properties and high toughness.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation

it.PP film

it.PP, kindly supplied from Sumitomo Chemical Co., Ltd., was compression molded at 180 °C, then quenched in ice water to obtain quenched *it*.PP film (Thickness: 0.1 mm). This film was used as a comparative sample, and as matrix in *all-it*.PP nanocomposite.

it.PP nanofibers

The well-aligned *it*.PP nanofibers was obtained by electrospinning a solution of 8 wt% *it*.PP in 1,2-dichlorobenzene with adding tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate, as an ionic substance for giving electrical conductivity. Electrospinning was carried out using a electrospinning unit (NF-104, MECC) with a heating unit and drum collector as shown in Fig.1. The distance between the needles tip and the collector was 30 cm and the applied voltage over the gap was 30 kV. *it*.PP solution in metallic syringe was heated at 120 °C by heating unit during electrospinning. The solution were fed by syringe pump with flow rate of 8.0 mL/h, and electrospun fibers were collected on the rotation drum (0~3000 rpm) with diameter of 20 cm. Then, the electrospun fiber bundles were drawn up to 9 times at 120 °C.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of electrospinning using heating unit and drum collector.

***all-it*.PP nanocomposite**

it.PP nanofibers (Draw ratio: 8 times) were impregnated between *it*.PP film through melt compression at 163 °C, the temperature between the melting point of film and the melting point of the nanofibers, then the sandwiched specimen was quenched in ice water to obtain quenched *all-it*.PP nanocomposite.

2.2 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to observe the surface morphology of nanofibers, fiber diameter, and the degree of fiber alignment with a JSM-5610LSV (JEOL Ltd., Japan), at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Pt was deposited on the surface prior to the observation.

Wide angle X-ray diffraction were carried out using the CuK α radiation, generated with an RINT-2000 (Rigaku Co.) at 40 kV, 20 mA. The X-ray beam was irradiated perpendicular to the surface of the specimen. The degree of orientation (Π) was evaluated from the X-ray diffraction photograph by the diffraction profiles of the (110) plane, after subtracting the air scattering. From the peak width at half maximum in the intensity profile (H) along the Debye-Scherrer ring, Π was calculated with following equation:

$$\Pi = \frac{180 - H}{180} \quad (1)$$

After subtracting the air scattering, the diffraction profile was curve resolved into noncrystalline scattering (O_{am}) and crystalline reflections (O_{cr}) using fityk multi-peaks separation software. The apparent crystallinity, X_c , was evaluated from their area ratio, with following equation:

$$X_c = \frac{O_{cr}}{O_{cr} + 1.297 \times O_{am}} \quad (2)$$

The crystallite size D was estimated using Scherrer's equation:

$$D = \frac{\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

where λ : X-ray wave length(1.5418 Å), β : the corrected integral width, θ : Bragg angle for the 110 reflection. The β value was calculated with the following equation:

$$\beta = B^2 - b^2 \quad (4)$$

where B : the observed value of integral width, b : integral width of silica standard.

The tensile test was conducted using a tensile tester (Autograph AGS-1kND (Shimadzu Co.)) with a cross head speed of 2 mm/min. More than five specimens were tested with the initial length of 20 mm. The cross-sectional area was determined from the density (floatation method with water / ethanol system at 30 °C), weight and length.

The optical transparency was measured by using double beam UV-vis spectrophotometer U-2000 (HITACHI Ltd.). The thickness of the sample was 200 μ m.

The melting point (T_m) was measured by a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) (Rigaku Co., DSC8230). Differential scanning thermographs were obtained from room temperature to 200°C, under a nitrogen atmosphere and a heating rate of 100 °C/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characteristics of *it*.PP nanofibers

Figure 2 shows SEM photographs of *it*.PP fibers collected with different rotating speed and the angular distributions of fibers along the rotating collector. The distributions are quantified by analyzing total of 100 fibers randomly selected from SEM photographs. SEM photographs revealed that all of the electrospun fibers on the rotating drum collector were smooth, nonporous and almost free of defects such as beads, by optimizing spinning conditions such as voltage, solution feed rate, heating temperature. The diameter of fibers is approximately 910 nm, when rotating speed of drum reached 3000 rpm. It can be observed that the degree of fibers alignment at 3000 rpm of rotating speed is the highest among that of these conditions. In addition, the distribution also shows that the fibers collected with the 3000 rpm were most highly aligned. With increasing the rotation speed, the degree of alignment increased.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs of *it*.PP nanofibers collected with different rotating speed and angular distribution of nanofibers. A total of 100 fibers randomly selected from SEM images were measured. Rotating speed of drum are a) 1000 rpm, b) 2000 rpm and c) 3000 rpm.

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrographs of *it*.PP nanofibers before and after drawing at 120 °C.

Figure 3 shows SEM photographs of *it*.PP nanofibers before and after drawing at 120 °C. The Fiber diameter decreased with increase of draw ratio, and the fiber diameter became approximately 660 nm after drawing 9 times.

Figure 4(a) shows X-ray diffraction photographs *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing at Figure 4: X-ray diffraction (a) photographs and (b) profiles of *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing at 120 °C.

120 °C. For the undrawn (As-spun) nanofibers, the reflection appeared as an isotropic and diffuse scattering, indicating mesophase with random orientation of *it.PP*. On the other hand, for the drawn nanofibers (draw ratio: 9 times), the reflections focused on the equatorial direction as a spot. This suggests that *it.PP* crystallites were highly oriented parallel to the drawn direction. The degree of orientation, being calculated from the azimuthal intensity distribution for the 110 reflection, increased with increasing the draw ratio. The drawn nanofibers with draw ratio of 9 showed high crystallite orientation (95%).

Figure 4(b) shows X-ray diffraction profiles integrated along the Debye-Scherrer ring of *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing at 120 °C. For the As-spun fibers, the mesophase scattering which is an intermediate phase of a crystal and amorphous appeared. On the other hand, for the drawn fibers, the crystalline profiles from α -form of *it.PP* appeared and increased with increasing the draw ratio. This suggests that structural transformation from mesophase to α -form occurred, and the crystallinity increased.

3.2 Mechanical properties of *it.PP* nanofibers

Figure 5(a) shows stress-strain curves of electrospun *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing, and (b) shows Young's modulus and tensile strength of the *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing. With the increases of crystallite orientation and crystallinity, with the increase of the draw ratio, Young's modulus and tensile strength of the *it.PP* nanofibers increased dramatically. As a result, Young's modulus and tensile strength of *it.PP* nanofibers (Draw ratio: 9 times) were found to be 12 times and 28 times higher than those of *it.PP* film.

Figure 5: (a) Stress-strain curves of electrospun *it.PP* nanofibers before and after drawing, and (b) Effect of drawing on Young's modulus and the tensile strength of electrospun *it.PP* nanofibers.

3.3 Melting temperature of *it.PP* nanofibers

Figure 6 shows the DSC thermographs of *it.PP* film and *it.PP* nanofibers (Draw ratio: 8 times). Compared with film, the melting point of the drawn nanofibers shifted to higher temperature. This makes it possible to prepare *all-it.PP* nanocomposites. In other words, drawn *it.PP* nanofibers were impregnated between *it.PP* through melt compression at the 163 °C (between the melting point of film (160.2 °C) and the melting point of the nanofibers (171.1 °C)), and compressed into *all-it.PP* nanocomposite.

Figure 6: DSC thermographs of *it.PP* film and *it.PP* nanofibers (Draw ratio: 8 times).

3.4 Characteristics of *all-it.PP* nanocomposite

Figure 7 shows the UV-vis spectra and the optical appearance of *it.PP* nanofibers (draw ratio: 8 times), *it.PP* film and *all-it.PP* nanocomposite. The *it.PP* film is well known to be very transparent. While, *it.PP* nanofibers is opaque. Compared with them, the nanocomposite is very transparent

optically. These observations suggest interface free structure for the composite, and the *it*.PP matrix surrounded the reinforcement *it*.PP nanofibers filled the spaces between the nanofibers.

Figure 7: UV-vis spectra and optical photographs of *it*.PP nanofibers (draw ratio: 8 times), *it*.PP film (thickness: 200 nm) and *all-it*.PP nanocomposite (thickness: 200 nm).

Figure 8(a) shows X-ray diffraction photographs and (b) the effect of compression time on the degree of crystallite orientation and X-ray crystallinity of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite. The reflections focused on the equatorial direction with the compression time. This suggests that *it*.PP matrix also oriented parallel to the direction of filled nanofibers, where the matrix epitaxially crystallized along the fibers looks like shish-kebab (as shown in the Figure 8(c)) even without shear stress.

Figure 8: (a) X-ray diffraction photographs, (b) the degree of crystallite orientation and X-ray crystallinity of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite, and (c) schematic illustration for formation of the structure looks like shish-kebab.

3.2 Mechanical properties of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite

Figure 9(a) shows stress-strain curves of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite (compression time: 60sec), and (b) shows the effect of compression time on Young's modulus and tensile strength of *all-it*.PP

nanocomposite. For *all-it*.PP nanocomposite, Young's modulus and tensile strength were both higher than those of *it*.PP film, and nanocomposite with press time of 60 sec showed the highest mechanical properties.

Table 1 shows Young's modulus, tensile strength and toughness of *it*.PP film and *all-it*.PP nanocomposite (compression time: 60sec). It was found that Young's modulus, tensile strength and toughness of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite were 2 times, 2times and 1.7 times higher than those of *it*.PP film, respectively.

Figure 9:(a) Stress-strain curves of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite (Press time: 60sec) and *it*.PP film, and (b) Effect of press time on Young's modulus and the tensile strength of *all-it*.PP nanocomposite.

	Young's modulus	Tensile strength	Toughness
	GPa	MPa	J/g
<i>it</i> .PP film	0.64	19.2	70.3
<i>All-it</i> .PP nanocomposite (Press time: 60sec)	1.25	35.8	116

Table 1: Young's modulus, tensile strength and toughness of *it*.PP film and *all-it*.PP nanocomposite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

By electrospinning under control of the solution viscosity by heating unit and solution conductivity by adding ionic substance, and post-drawing, well-aligned and well-oriented *it*.PP nanofibers were obtained. By the increases of crystallite orientation and crystallinity, with increasing the draw ratio, this *it*.PP nanofibers possess significantly higher mechanical properties than *it*.PP film. Furthermore, compared to the film, these drawn nanofibers showed higher melting temperature. This made it possible to prepare *all-it*.PP nanocomposites, by using these nanofibers as reinforcement. This recyclable composite showed high optical transparency, high mechanical properties and high toughness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research from the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science.

REFERENCES

- [1] Polypropylene Handbook 2nd Edition, N.Pasquini ed., Hanser Pub. Cincinnati, 2005.
- [2] J. Leng, A. K. Lou, *Multifunctional Polymer Nanocomposites*, CRC press, Florida, 2011.
- [3] N. J. Capiati, R. S. Porter, The concept of one polymer composites modelled with high density polyethylene, *Journal of Materials Science*, **10**, 1975, pp. 1671-1677.
- [4] R.J.Yan, P.J.Hine, I.M.Ward, R.H.Olley, D.C.Bassett, The hot compaction of SPECTRA gel-spun polyethylene fibre, *J. Mater. Sci.* **32**, 1997, pp.4821-4832.
- [5] P.J.Hine, I.M.Ward, N.D.Jordan, R.H. Olley, D.C.Bassett, The hot compaction behaviour of woven oriented polypropylene fibres and tapes. I. Mechanical properties, *Polymer* **44**, 2003, pp.1117-1131.
- [6] T.Peijs, Composites for recyclability, *Mater. Today*, **6**, 2003, pp.30-35.
- [7] B.Alcock, N.O. Cabrera, N.M.Barkoula, T.Peijs, The mechanical properties of unidirectional all-polypropylene composites, *Composites A*, **37**, 2006, pp.716-726
- [8] T. Nishino, I. Matsuda, K. Hirao, All-Cellulose Composite, *Macromolecules*, **37**, 2004, pp. 7683-7687.
- [9] T. Nishino, N. Arimoto, All-cellulose composite prepared by selective dissolving of fiber surface, *Biomacromolecules*, **8**, 2007, pp. 2712-2716.
- [10] J. M. Zhang, Z. Mousavi, N. Soykeabkaew, P. Smith, T. Nishino, T. Peijs, All-Aramid Composites by Partial Fiber Dissolution, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **2**, 2010, pp. 919-926.
- [11] J.Doshi, D. H. Reneker, Electrospinning Process and Applications of Electrospun Fibers, *Journal of Electrostatics*, **35**, 1995, pp. 151-160.
- [12] N. Bhardwaj and S. C. Kundu, Electrospinning: A fascinating fiber fabrication technique, *Biotechnology Advances*, **28**, 2010, pp. 325-347.
- [13] M. V. Kakade, S. Givens, K. Gardner, K. H. Lee, D. B. Chase, J. F. Rabolt, Electric Field Induced Orientation of Polymer Chains in Macroscopically Aligned Electrospun Polymer Nanofibers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **129**, 2007, pp. 2777-2782.
- [14] H. Tsuji, M. Nakano, M. Hashimoto, K. Takashima, S. Katsura, A. Mizuno, Electrospinning of Poly (lactic acid) Stereocomplex Nanofibers, *Biomacromolecules*, **7**, 2006, pp. 3316-3320.
- [15] X. Zong, K. Kim, D. Fang, S. Ran, B. S. Hsiao, B. Chu, Structure and process relationship of electrospun bioabsorbable nanofiber membranes, *Polymer*, **43**, 2002, pp.4403-4412
- [16] J. Lyons, C. Li, F. Ko, Melt-electrospinning part I: processing parameters and geometric properties, *Polymer*, **45**, 2004, pp. 7597-7603.